

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL REHABILITATION AND SOCIAL ADAPTATION MEASURES IN CRIME PREVENTION

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Annotation

The article describes the content and importance of social rehabilitation and social adaptation measures in crime prevention, as well as the legal basis of social rehabilitation and social adaptation in crime prevention through the analysis of legislation in this area.

Keywords: Crime Prevention, Social Rehabilitation, Social Adaptation, Non-Social Behavior, Victim

As a result of reforms implemented in the judicial system in our country in recent years, based on humane principles, criminal punishments are reduced, and more non-custodial punishments are used for criminals. Through these reforms, based on humane principles, criminal penalties are reduced and more non-custodial sentences are applied to offenders. This will certainly allow them to realize their mistake, return to a healthy lifestyle in the future, and most importantly, be in the arms of their family.

Also, Decree No. PF-6196 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 "On measures to raise the activity of internal affairs bodies to a new level in terms of quality in the field of ensuring public safety and fighting crime" and "On approval of the concept of public safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for its implementation" dated 29.11.2021 We can tell about the changes made in the field of probation with Decree No. PF-27.

the concept of social rehabilitation and social adjustment, it is appropriate to be aware of the meaning of the word "rehabilitation" and the areas in which this concept is used. The word "rehabilitation" is derived from the Latin word "rehabilitatio" which means "to restore". The concept of rehabilitation is used not only in the legal field, but also in the medical and social fields.

In particular, medical rehabilitation means a set of medical, pedagogical, psychological measures aimed at restoring the impaired functioning of the body,

the working capacity of patients and disabled people. Social rehabilitation means a set of measures aimed at restoring the lost or limited social rights of a person or a group of persons due to disability, migration, human trafficking, unemployment and other similar problems.

Application of social rehabilitation and social adjustment measures Social rehabilitation and social adjustment measures are applied to victims of offenses, persons prone to committing offenses, and persons who have committed offenses by the sectoral services that directly implement the prevention of offenses in accordance with the procedure established by law.

When the concept of "social rehabilitation" is used in relation to the offender, it is directly manifested in measures such as moral correction or removal of the criminal record. "Social adjustment" is expressed in cases such as the placement of a person who has returned from a penal institution to study or work, providing housing for a certain period of time, providing material assistance by special commissions under the authorities, as well as legal assistance by law enforcement agencies [1].

Particular attention is paid to the creation of an infrastructure to help and provide comprehensive assistance to persons who are in a serious social situation, including those who have suffered as a result of offenses committed as a result of physical, moral or property damage. In particular, a regional branch of the Rehabilitation and Adaptation Center was established in Tashkent. The center provides legal advice on protecting women from violence and harassment, and provides medical and psychological assistance.

We can include the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 29, 2010 "On the prevention of delinquency and offenses among minors" as a legal basis aimed at victimological prevention of offenses committed within the framework of family relations. This law prevents minors from being unsupervised, neglecting, committing crimes or other antisocial behavior, identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions that allow them to do so; ensure protection of rights, freedoms and legal interests of minors; formation of law-abiding behavior in minors; socio-pedagogical rehabilitation of minors and families in a socially dangerous situation; regulates the performance of tasks such as identifying cases of involvement of minors in committing offenses or other anti-social acts and putting an end to them.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Prevention of Offenses" dated May 14, 2014 [2] is the primary legal basis for social rehabilitation and social adjustment in the prevention of offenses. According to this law, among the main

tasks of crime prevention is to identify the causes of crimes and the conditions that make them possible, to study them, to take measures to eliminate them, and to prevent crimes from occurring .

Social rehabilitation and social adjustment of victims, those prone to commit crimes, those who have committed crimes, including previously convicted and released from places of deprivation of liberty, reducing the risk of individuals becoming victims of crimes, directly implementing and participating in the prevention of crimes ensuring mutual cooperation of the activities of bodies and institutions and coordinating their activities.

This Law provides a number of definitions for some elements of crime prevention. Including

social rehabilitation and social adjustment - to provide legal, social, psychological, medical, pedagogical and other types of assistance to victims of crime, antisocial behavior, prone to committing crimes, persons who have committed crimes, as well as the norms of behavior accepted in society and a set of measures aimed at inculcating the rules;

antisocial behavior - lifestyle, action or inaction of a person that violates the norms and rules of behavior accepted in society;

offense - a culpable illegal act (action or inaction) for which administrative or criminal liability is provided;

a victim of a crime - a person who suffered a crime as a result of physical, moral or property damage;

In the literature on crime prevention², it is emphasized that a person prone to committing a crime is the study of individuals who are in a state of possibility of committing a crime due to the danger of their antisocial behavior.

It can be seen from this that social rehabilitation and social adjustment is the provision of legal, social, psychological, medical, pedagogical and other types of assistance to victims of crime, antisocial behavior, prone to committing crimes, and persons who have committed crimes, as well as the behavior accepted by them in society. - social rehabilitation and social adaptation to life based on measures aimed at inculcating norms and rules of behavior, serves as a major direction for identifying and eliminating future violations, as well as determining the causes of violations and the conditions that allow them to occur.

of the Law on the Prevention of Offenses

, and after studying the procedure of serving the sentence of the convicts serving the sentence in the Probation Service, in cooperation with the employees of the Probation Service, takes measures for their social rehabilitation and social

adjustment, i.e. the persons serving the sentence of correctional works helps in finding a job and takes measures to adapt the spouse to social life by monitoring the place of regular residence.

President Sh. M.Mirziyoev at the solemn meeting dedicated to the International Women's Day on March 8: "... 155 centers for the rehabilitation and adjustment of victims of violence in the regions in order to protect the rights of women, "Hotlines" was established. In the past short period, an effective system was created in our country to go from house to house, study the socio-spiritual environment, and solve existing problems. Based on this system, in 2020, the problems of more than 47 thousand 690 women living in difficult conditions, as well as 13 thousand 344 women with disabilities were studied on the spot"³.

At the same time, in practice, measures cannot be delayed to further ensure the rights of citizens, especially women who need help, to strengthen the practical relations of state bodies with institutions of civil society, including mass media, and to continue the introduction of public control in these matters. Some problems and shortcomings remain that require consideration.

Based on this, the following are identified as priorities for social rehabilitation and adjustment, as well as improvement of the system of prevention of family and domestic violence:

early prevention of family and interpersonal conflicts, depressive situations that can provoke suicidal behavior and other situations that negatively affect the moral and moral environment in society, as well as ensuring the participation of the general public in this process;

in establishing a system of social rehabilitation and adjustment, formation of mutual cooperation of state bodies, including the formation of an effective system of cooperation with civil society institutions, in solving conflicting situations that arise, primarily family-domestic conflicting situations; wide involvement of civil society institutions in the early prevention of conflict situations, first of all, in the improvement of the system of social rehabilitation and adaptation by providing targeted support to individuals and families in the "risk group";

to determine and study the causes of conflict situations, including the use of family-domestic violence, the factors that provoke a suicidal mood, and take measures to eliminate them;

regarding any form of family-domestic violence in the society, first of all, by ensuring an atmosphere of intolerant attitude by close relatives, including the

inevitability of punishment, to find a solution by supporting persons in a difficult social situation;

it is required to increase legal consciousness and legal culture in society, to strengthen legitimacy in the field of family and interpersonal relations, to strengthen the sense of involvement in the processes of social rehabilitation and adaptation. 4

Establishing a system of social rehabilitation and adaptation, as a result of its effectiveness, family and interpersonal conflicts that can provoke suicidal behavior and other situations that have a negative impact on the moral and moral environment in society and in the family, any form of family-domestic violence in society , makes the greatest contribution to increasing legal awareness and legal culture in society.

The orders and decisions of the ministries, state committees and agencies determine the powers of the relevant ministries, state committees and agencies in the field of prevention of delinquency and delinquency among minors, as well as relevant procedures. In particular, according to the order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 18 dated January 17, 2011 "Identification, registration, examination and medical and social rehabilitation of minors who regularly consume alcohol, narcotic drugs, psychotropic or other substances that affect the activity of the mind" "Regulation on the procedure for conducting medical examinations of minors placed in specialized educational institutions" was approved by order No. 342 of December 17, 2010 . 5

In this regulation , powers in the field of prevention of lack of control and offenses among minors, issues of cooperation with other organizations, and procedures for conducting medical examinations are determined .

Identification, registration, examination and medical and social rehabilitation of minors who regularly consume alcohol, narcotic drugs, psychotropic or other substances affecting mental activity is one of the main tasks of health authorities. It is required to identify minors who regularly consume narcotic drugs, psychotropic or other substances that affect mental activity, and their place of residence and conditions. For this reason, it is important to provide this activity of health authorities with information.

Also, providing assistance in the employment of minors released from penal institutions or returning from specialized educational institutions and improving their living conditions, assistance in determining the forms of placement of other minors in need of state assistance, as well as in the legal acts

on the social rehabilitation of minors it is indicated to carry out other works provided for.

The competences of crime prevention units in the field of state policy regarding youth include participation in the development and implementation of state programs, regional and other programs in the field of state policy regarding youth, participation in activities aimed at raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of young people, prevention of offenses among young people, including to determine the reasons for the commission of offenses and the conditions that make it possible, to eliminate them, to take measures for social rehabilitation and social adjustment of young citizens, to identify persons who are prone to commit offenses among students and to carry out social rehabilitation and social adjustment in relation to them 6 it is determined to take measures.

medical and social rehabilitation of minors who regularly consume alcohol, narcotic drugs, psychotropic or other substances that affect mental activity , alcohol, narcotic drugs, psychotropic or mental activity identification, registration, examination, treatment and organization of medical and social rehabilitation of minors who regularly use other harmful substances are carried out by health management bodies and health institutions.

Qualified medical and narcological assistance, consisting of medical examination, medical advice, diagnosis, treatment, and medical and social rehabilitation services for the treatment of their illness, must be provided to minors under the care and supervision of the dispensary.

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 17, 2018, aimed at further improving the system of social and household provision and employment of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty, and increasing the effectiveness of preventive and other measures to provide assistance to these persons. Decision No. 543 "On practical measures to further improve the household provision and employment system" was adopted.

this decision , the "Road Map" for 2018-2022 on improving the system of rehabilitation and social adaptation of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty was approved and the main directions and tasks of improving the system of social and household provision and employment of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty were approved. defined: improvement of the institutional and organizational-legal basis of the activities of the structures responsible for the social adaptation of persons released from

places of deprivation of liberty, clearly demarcating their tasks, functions and powers;

social adaptation of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty, including improving the quality and level of their life;

formation of a monitoring system of psychological and social adaptation of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty;

development of social partnership between state bodies and institutions of civil society within the framework of implementation of works in the field of social adaptation and rehabilitation of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty;

development of a public-private partnership system between state bodies and business entities, which provides for the provision of appropriate benefits to persons released from places of deprivation of liberty by involving private sector representatives in the process of rehabilitation;

preparation, forecasting and planning of psychological, social and household maintenance and employment activities of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty;

taking effective measures aimed at reducing the number of recidivism and repeated crimes, strengthening the system of early prevention of offenses⁷. It can be seen that the application of the most alternative ways of adaptation to social life, the implementation of functional ways of returning to a healthy household life based on the mutual cooperation of state bodies and business entities are recognized as urgent tasks .

Rehabilitation and social adaptation centers for persons released from places of deprivation of liberty were established on the basis of centers for social adaptation of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty and released from special commandant's account, and they were assigned the following tasks: organizing and ensuring social protection of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty, satisfying their primary needs by providing one-time allowances for clothing, food and accommodation;

creating acceptable social and household conditions, receiving help from specialists (psychologist, medical worker, lawyer, etc.), providing referrals for treatment, homes for the elderly and the disabled;

providing assistance in rehabilitation, in solving housing and household and other social and household problems, in obtaining benefits established by law.

assistance is provided to convicts in the matter of documentation (restoration of personal documents, obtaining a passport), their pension insurance, registration of labor records until the person is released from the penal institutions.

to study the quality of adaptation to social life within a year from the moment of release of the person from the penal institution. 8

Centers of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and special commissions for providing assistance to persons released from places of deprivation of liberty in the social and household sphere and providing employment, in cooperation with internal affairs bodies and self-government bodies of citizens, socio-economic assistance to persons released from penal institutions develops and approves individual programs of rendering, as well as examines on a monthly basis the implementation of individual programs of social and legal assistance to this category of persons on the basis of a court decision.

Based on the above information, we can conclude as follows, rather than fighting against crime, it is more important to determine the causes and conditions of violations and to take measures to prevent and eliminate them, first of all, it is important to ensure moral correction, social rehabilitation and social adjustment of offenders.

Establishment of rehabilitation centers for persons without permanent residence and establishment in each district, as well as establishment of medical personnel to carry out their activities in the building of this institution, will serve to achieve a positive result.

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